

Unperturbed Dimension of Polymer Molecules from Viscosity Measurements in Different Solvents

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An equation for the determination of cross-over point concentration, C_x , in the plot C/η_{sp} vs. C of a polymer in a number of solvents has been derived and an expression relating C_x with the unperturbed dimension of polymer molecules, $(r_0^{-2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, has been proposed. Unperturbed dimensions calculated for polymethyl methacrylate, polyvinyl acetate and polystyrene with this new expression are in good agreement with the literature values.

Unperturbed dimension of polymer molecules is generally determined either by (i) measuring viscosity of polymer solutions at the θ -temperature¹ or by (ii) building up suitable expressions²⁻⁵ relating the intrinsic viscosity with molecular weight and following an extrapolation procedure in view of mathematical necessity.

In the present communication, a new equation has been proposed for the determination of unperturbed dimension of polymer molecules from a knowledge of the cross-over point concentration.

Cross-over point concentration : Eirich and Riseman⁶ showed that the plot of slope vs. intercept of Huggins'⁷ linear equation, $\eta_{sp}/C = [\eta] + k'[\eta]^2C$ for a polymer in different solvents gives a straight line. It has been shown by Streeter and Boyer⁸ that the existence of such a linear relationship between slope and intercept necessitates that the plots of η_{sp}/C vs. C for a polymer in different solvents should meet at a common point, the corresponding concentration at the convergence point being called "*the cross-over point concentration*". Evidently, it was felt that the parameter derived at such a cross-over point should be independent of solvent and is an inherent property of the polymer alone. Cleverdon and Smith⁹ have shown that the η_{sp}/C value at such a cross-over point is related to the intrinsic viscosity at the precipitation point. Similar attempts have been made by Gundiah *et al.*¹⁰ though

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they started with the Kraemer's equation¹¹. Their procedure, however, is more realistic in view of the fact that the cross-over concentration in Kraemer's plot is on the positive side of the concentration axis, whereas the cross-over point concentration in Cleverdon and Smith's method is on the negative side of the concentration axis. Gundiah *et al.* have observed that the intrinsic viscosity at the cross-over point concentration is almost equal to the intrinsic viscosity at the precipitation point in a θ -solvent. No attempt has, however, been made to correlate the cross-over point concentration with other inherent properties of the polymer.

Cross-over point concentration from Huggins' Equation : By applying Stokes' law to the polymer solutions Huggins deduced the equation

$$\eta_{sp}/C = [\eta] + k'[\eta]^2 C \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_{sp} = specific viscosity, C = concentration in gm/dl.

$[\eta]$ = intrinsic viscosity and k' = Huggins' constant.

The significance of the constant k' has been discussed elaborately by Eirich *et al.*⁶. They have explained the variation of k' , though constant for a polymer-solvent system, with the change of solvent introducing the concept of back-coiling mechanism. Now, let us consider the equation of cross-over point concentration in the Huggins' plot. If C_x be the concentration at which all the η_{sp}/C vs. C curves meet when extrapolated, then at C_x ,

$$(\eta_{sp}/C)_x = [\eta]_1 + k'_1[\eta]_1^2 C_x = [\eta]_2 + k'_2[\eta]_2^2 C_x \dots = P_x \text{ (say)}$$

In general,

$$[\eta]_i + k'_i[\eta]_i^2 C_x = P_x$$

or

$$k'_i[\eta]_i^2 = P_x/C_x - [\eta]_i/C_x = \alpha + \sigma[\eta]_i \quad \dots (2)$$

Equation (2) is the well known *Eirich-Riseman relationship*. Validity of this equation has been tested by many workers^{8,9,12} though the direct value of C_x has been obtained only in a few cases^{8,9}. The expression for α and σ have been given by Bhatnagar *et al.*¹³ introducing the theory of rate process to viscous flow. Recently, Ibrahim¹⁴ has shown both theoretically and experimentally the approximate nature of the Huggins' equation as compared to the empirical equation of Schulz and Blaschke¹⁵, considering the parent equation, η_{sp}/C

$= \frac{[\eta]}{1 - k[\eta]C}$, obtained by an extension of Kuhn's hydrodynamic treatment.

Evidently,

$$\eta_{sp}/C = [\eta] + k[\eta]^2 C + k^2[\eta]^3 C^2 + \dots \approx [\eta] + k[\eta]^2 C \text{ (at low concentration)} \quad \dots (1)$$

(Huggins' Equation)

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whereas, without neglecting any term, one obtains,

$$\eta_{sp}/C = [\eta] + k[\eta]\eta_{sp} \quad \dots (3)$$

(*Schulz Blaschke Equation*)

From the derivation, it is evident that equation (3) involves no approximation and should be regarded as an equation of choice so far as a two parameter equation relating viscosity and concentration is concerned.

As is expected k' differs significantly from k , sometimes as high as 300%¹⁴. Since the values of k' and k are obtained by dividing the slopes of equation (1) and (3) by $[\eta]^2$ and $[\eta]$ respectively, any error in the value of $[\eta]$ will influence the values of these parameters. An equation which gives k directly, but fundamentally the same as in equation (3) is that proposed by Heller¹⁶.

$$C/\eta_{sp} = \frac{1}{[\eta]} - kC \quad \dots (4)$$

The important aspect about this equation is that it gives directly the value of k as the slope and is thus unaffected by any error in $[\eta]$ values. The constancy of the value of k in fractionated polystyrene samples varying in molecular weights is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Data showing the constancy of k (according to Heller's method) for polystyrene varying in molecular weight in benzene (a).

Fraction No.	$[\eta]$	k
Fr-1	1.408	0.2087
Fr-2	1.538	0.2120
Fr-3	1.626	0.2000
Fr-4	1.688	0.2120
Fr-5	1.905	0.2100
Fr-6	1.961	0.1980
Fr-7	2.031	0.1980
Fr-8	2.198	0.2008
Fr-9	2.326	0.2000

(a) Data from our laboratory. Viscosity measured at $35^\circ \pm 0.02 C$ in an Ostwald Viscometer.

Cross-over point concentration from Heller's Equation : Let us consider the condition for a cross-over point concentration in equation (4). Proceeding as before,

$$(C_x/\eta_{sp})_x = \frac{1}{[\eta]_1} - k_1 C_x = \frac{1}{[\eta]_2} - k_2 C_x = \dots = P \text{ (say)}$$

So, at the cross-over point

$$1/[\eta]_c - k_1 C_c = P$$

or

$$1/[\eta] = P + k_2 C_c \quad \dots (5)$$

Therefore, the condition that the plots of C/η_{sp} vs. C for a polymer in different solvents should meet at a common point necessitates that the plot of $1/[\eta]$ vs. k for different solvents should be linear. That such a linear relationship does exist has been demonstrated in Fig. 3 from data (Tables 2, 3 and 4) taken from literature. The actual convergence of C/η_{sp} vs. C plot at a point has been shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

C/η_{sp} vs C PLOT FOR POLYSTYRENE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS (FIG 1)

C/η_{sp} vs C PLOT FOR POLYMETHYL METHACRYLATE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

(Fig. 2)

TABLE 2

The cross-over point concentration derived from $1/[\eta]$ vs k in case of polymethyl methacrylate (Molecular weight = 406,000)²⁷

Solvent	$1/[\eta]$	k	C_x gm/dl
Benzene	0.783	0.3160	
Toluene	1.140	0.4000	2.60
Chloroform	0.553	0.2200	
Acetone	1.441	0.5450	
Amyl-methyl Ketone	2.595	0.9880	

TABLE 3

The cross-over point concentration derived from $1/[\eta]$ vs k plot in case of polyvinyl acetate. (Molecular weight = 250,000)²⁸

Solvent	$1/[\eta]$	k	C_x gm/dl
Chloroform	1.0000	0.3333	
S-tetrachloro ethane	1.0885	0.3571	
Methylene chloride	1.2350	0.3845	3.50
Acetophenone	1.6100	0.5005	
Chlorobenzene	1.8505	0.5895	

TABLE 4

The cross-over point concentration derived from $1/[\eta]$ vs. k plot in case of polystyrene⁸

Solvent	$1/[\eta]$	k	C_x gm/dl
Benzene	0.730	0.2000	
Toluene	0.790	0.2200	3.59
Ethyl benzene	0.881	0.2333	
MEK	1.520	0.4333	
Ethyl acetate	1.642	0.4500	
Decalin	1.800	0.6000	

Significance of the cross-over point concentration: In order to obtain the theoretical significance of the cross-over point concentration, we have followed the approach of Bhatnagar *et al.*¹³, who have derived the expression for the relative viscosity, η_{rel} , considering equivalent sphere model for polymer molecules in solutions. Without making any approximation in the expressions of fluidities as was done by Bhatnagar *et al.*, we obtain

$$\eta_{rel} = e^{x_2\gamma/RT} [1 - x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\}]^{-1} \quad \dots (6)$$

where the symbols have got the same meaning as those used by Eyring¹⁷ and Bhatnagar *et al.*¹³.

So, one can write,

$$\begin{aligned} 1/\eta_{sp} = 1/(\eta_{rel}-1) &= \frac{1}{e^{x_2\gamma/RT} [1 - x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\}]^{-1} - 1} \\ &= \frac{1 - x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\}}{e^{x_2\gamma/RT} - 1 + x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\}} \\ &= \frac{1 - x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\}}{x_2\{1 - \omega(p)F(y)\} + \gamma/RT} \end{aligned}$$

(considering dilute solutions). Putting the value for x_2 (according to reference, 13)

$$1/\eta_{sp} = \frac{1}{9.347 \times 10^{20} (\bar{r}^2)^{3/2} / M \{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT\} C} - \frac{1 - \omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT}$$

$$\text{or, } C/\eta_{sp} = \frac{1}{9.347 \times 10^{20} (\bar{r}^2)^{3/2} / M \{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT\}} - \frac{1 - \omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT} \cdot C$$

$$\text{or } C/\eta_{sp} = 1/[\eta] - kC$$

$$\text{where } [\eta] = 9.347 \times 10^{20} (\bar{r}^2)^{3/2} / M \{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT\}$$

an expression exactly identical with that derived by Bhatnagar *et al.*, and

$$k = \frac{1 - \omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} 1/[\eta] &= \frac{1}{9.347 \times 10^{20}(\bar{r}^2)^{3/2}/M\{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT\}} \\ &= \frac{A}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$A = \frac{1}{9.347 \times 10^{20}(\bar{r}^2)^{3/2}/M}$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned} 1/[\eta] &= A \left[\frac{1 - \omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT} + \frac{\omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT} \right] \\ &= Ak + B \end{aligned} \quad \dots (7)$$

where

$$B = \frac{A \omega(p)F(y)}{1 - \omega(p)F(y) + \gamma/RT}$$

Though the expression for B seems to be a solvent dependent one, the numerical value of B ($B \approx 0$) is so small due to the extremely small value of $\omega(p)F(y)$ in dilute solution, it is quite reasonable to take B as a constant.

According to equation (7), the slope of $1/[\eta]$ against k plot should give the value of A . Comparing equations (5) and (7) it will be observed that,

$$\begin{aligned} C_x &= \text{Cross-over point concentration} = A \\ &= [9.347 \times 10^{20}(\bar{r}^2)^{3/2}/M]^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (8)$$

If we assume that $(\bar{r}^2)^{\ddagger} = (r_0^2)^{\ddagger}$ becomes the unperturbed root mean square end-to-end distance, then

$$(\bar{r}_0^2)^{\ddagger} = 2.204 \times 10^{-8}(M/C_0)^{1/3} \quad \dots (9)$$

where C_0 = cross-over conc. in g/ml. = $0.01C_x$.

This equation is strikingly similar to the equation (10) derived by Cornet¹⁸ considering a uniform segment density of polymer molecules at the critical concentration, C_{cr} .

$$(\bar{r}_0^2)^{\ddagger} = 2.84 \times 10^{-8}(M/C_{cr})^{1/3} \quad \dots (10)$$

The values of $(\bar{r}_0^2/M)^{\ddagger}$ calculated by equation (9) for polymethyl methacrylate, polyvinyl acetate and polystyrene are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5

Comparison of $(\bar{r}_0^2/M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ values calculated by equation (9) with literature data

Polymer	Molecular weight	$C_0 \times 10^2$ gm/ml	$(\bar{r}_0^2/M)^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^{11}$	
			Calculated by eqn. (9)	Literature
Polymethyl methacrylate	406,000	2.720	852	780(a)
Polyvinyl acetate	250,000	3.315	865	843(b)
Polystyrene	370,000	3.60	785	735(c)
(a) Ref.—(29).				
(b) Ref.—(30).				
(c) Ref.—(31).				

It will be evident from the table that the values of $(\bar{r}_0^2/M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ calculated by using the cross-over concentration are of the right order and fairly in good agreement with the values given in the literature.

DISCUSSIONS

In the derivation of our final equation (9) we have assumed that $(\bar{r}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ becomes $(\bar{r}_0^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ at the cross-over point concentration. Validity for such an assumption is supported by the fact that at this unique concentration, the viscosity parameters are independent of the solvents. It has been shown theoretically by Fixman¹⁹, Yamakawa²⁰, Krigbaum²¹, Grimley²² and Cornet¹⁸ that the expansion parameter, α , decreases with increasing concentration of polymer solutions. Therefore, there is a possibility that at a certain concentration the expansion parameter attains a value of unity corresponding to the unperturbed dimension of the polymer molecules. Maron *et al.*^{23,24} have shown that the total effective volume of a polymer molecule in a solution at higher concentration is independent of the solvent used and that the molecules attain their unperturbed dimension at such concentrations. The values of C_c obtained for different polymers with the help of equation (5) are on the higher concentration range comparable to the values of C_{cr} obtained by Cornet.

Determination of unperturbed dimension by the θ -temperature method is not popular in view of the fact that the determination of the θ -temperature in a convenient range of polymer-solvent system is rather cumbersome. As for the other methods, there is much controversy about the exact expression of the expansion parameter, α . It has been shown by Cornet²⁵ and Burchard²⁶ that it is almost impossible to determine unperturbed dimension

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from experimentally determined perturbed values. In view of these facts, our expression as well as Cornet's expression for determination of unperturbed dimension, $(\bar{r}_0^2)^\dagger$ appears promising.

In using our equation (9) for the determination of $(\bar{r}_0^2)^\dagger$ one has, however, to bear the following point in mind. The derivation of C_x is based on Heller's equation which is applicable in dilute solution only where the plot of C/η_{sp} vs. C is linear. In determining $1/[\eta]$ and k values for the evaluation of C_x , one should, therefore, be critical in selecting values considering only the narrow range of linearity of C/η_{sp} vs. C plot.

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